

Spectrophotometric Studies of some Bis-azo- β -diketone Compounds and their Ionisation Constants in Mixed Buffer Solutions

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A series of bis-azo compounds have been prepared from *m*- and *p*-phenylenediamine and β -diketones. The electronic absorption spectra of the compounds have been studied in organic solvents of different polarities. The effect of medium on band position and band assignment has been considered. The ir and ¹H nmr spectra are discussed in relation to molecular structure. The spectral changes in buffer solution of pH \approx 2–12 were used for calculating the pK_a values of the bis-azo compounds under study.

Despite the fact that azo compounds have been widely studied, not much is reported in the literature about the spectral behaviour of bisazocompounds derived from β -diketones. Some studies on the effect of the nature of the organic solvent on the spectra of azo dyes were performed^{1,2} and the determination of the pK_a values determined³.

The present investigation considers the electronic absorption spectra of some bis-azo compounds in organic solvents and buffer solutions containing 30% dioxane. It is attempted to clarify the relation between molecular structure and ir as well as ¹H nmr spectral behaviour of the compounds.

Results and Discussion

Absorption spectra of bis-azo compounds in ethanol : The spectra of compounds (a–e) reveal two bands at 212–216 and 244–252 nm which are due to ¹L_a \leftarrow ¹A and ¹L_b \leftarrow ¹A transitions of the phenyl ring. These two bands are insensitive towards the nature of solvents. The third band at 374–440 nm is of high absorptivity; it is influenced by the type of the group (R) of

m-Bis-azobenzene-di(β -diketone) :

p-Bis-azobenzene-di(β -diketone) :

the pentanedione part of the molecule and the nature of the organic solvent. This band can be assigned to a charge transfer interaction within the whole molecule. The CT band of compound seems to be composite one and appears sometimes as a band and a shoulder in case of compound (e) at 303 and 440 nm. This can be attributed

to the possible tautomeric shift liable to occur in these compounds as shown in Scheme 1.

azo-hydrazo equilibrium
Scheme 1

The replacement of CH_3 by the phenyl ring shifts the CT band to longer wavelength due to the extended delocalisation of electrons through the molecule. This gives a support for the charge transfer nature of this band in combination with the $\pi-\pi^*$ transition of the azo group¹.

Solvent effects : The spectra of compound (e) in different organic solvents are presented in Fig. 1. It is clear that the CT band shows a wide variation in its position with changing the solvent polarity supporting the CT nature of the band.

The band displacement can be discussed in

Fig. 1. Spectra of $5 \times 10^{-5} M$ of *p*-bisazobenzene-di(acetylbenzoylmethane) in different organic solvents. (1) ethanol (sat.), (2) methanol (sat.) (3) dioxane, (4) acetonitrile, (5) acetone, (6) CCl_4 (sat.), (7) CHCl_3 , (8) ether (sat.) and (9) cyclohexane (sat.).

terms of macroscopic solvent polarity via dielectric constant and also refractive index. On applying the Gati- Szalay equation⁴, the plots of $\Delta\nu$ (cm^{-1}) vs $(D-1)/(D+1)$ or $F(n)$ shown non-linear relationship. Also, using the functions given by Suppan⁵ it is found that plots of λ_{max} of the CT band vs $F(D)$ or $\phi(D)$ or $F_2(n)$ are not linear, indicating that neither the dielectric constant nor the refractive index of the solvents are the main factors causing the shifts of the band.

The plots of λ_{max} vs the microscopic solvent polarity parameters z and E_T , are linear for compounds (a, d, e) but non-linear for (b, c). Plots of λ_{max} vs the microscopic parameters α and β , the parameters of Taft and Kamlet⁶ indicating the acidity and basicity of the protic and aprotic solvents respectively, are straight lines but deviate from linearity for compounds (b, d). The linearity of this relation indicates that the hydrogen bond donor solvent (α) or hydrogen bond acceptor solvent (β) supports the occurrence of the specific association through proton-acceptor systems. Accordingly, it can be concluded that spectral displacement of the CT band with changed solvent is the combined result of the dielectric properties of the medium and changed solvation of the ground and excited states as well as intermolecular hydrogen bonding between the solvent molecules and n -electrons of the azo group or oxygen of the carbonyl group of the solute molecule.

Infrared spectra : The band assignment is made using the reported methods⁷. The assignments of important bands are given in Table 1. The ν_{OH} band indicates an intramolecular H-bond. The $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ band at $1505-1510 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for the bis-azo dyes gives an indication of the existence of azo \rightleftharpoons hydrazo equilibrium in the solid state.

¹H nmr spectra : ¹H nmr spectra data of the compounds are given in Table 2. The weak signals at δ 14.68, 14.74 and 13.55 ppm for

TABLE 1—ASSIGNMENT OF IMPORTANT IR BANDS OF THE BIS-AZO- β -DIKETONE DERIVATIVES (a-e)

Assignment	a	b	c	d	e
ν_{OH}	3 400	3 360	3 060	3 480	3 440
ν_{C-H} of CH_3	2 820	2 930	—	2 930	2 925
$\nu_{C=O}$					
<i>assym.</i>	1 648	1 675	1 644	1 640	1 672
$\nu_{C=C}$					
<i>conjugation</i>	1 600	1 603	1 598	1 598	1 620
<i>assym.</i>					
$\delta_{C=N}$					
<i>assym.</i>	1 510	1 509	1 510	1 505	1 509
$\nu_{N=N}$					
<i>sym.</i>	1 418	1 412	1 400	1 415	1 425
δ_{OH}	1 365	1 358	1 328	1 368	1 360
β_{C-H}	1 192	1 180	1 210	1 200	1 180
<i>aromatic sym.</i>					
ν_{C-O}					
<i>sym.</i>	1 127	1 125	1 153	1 028	1 052
γ_{C-H}	980	980	990	980	982
<i>aromatic</i>	(878–	(931–	(930–	(885–	(932–
<i>sym. and</i>	690)	600)	684)	600)	615)
<i>assym.</i>					

compounds **a**, **b**, **c** respectively, are removed by deuteration indicating that they correspond to the OH-group. The signal appearing at δ 1.9–2.2 ppm is due to the methine group. The appearance of both signals due to OH and CH groups confirms the occurrence of the ketoenol equilibrium. Proton-7 has only *meta*-coupling and its signal is shown at very high fields in the spectrum supporting the presence of this proton *ortho* to the azo group. Proton-3 has *ortho*- and *meta*-coupling whereas that of proton-4 has only *ortho*-coupling. The signal of the protons of CH_3 of (**a**) is of high integration area which decreased in (**b**) and disappeared in case of (**c**). This behaviour is also shown in case of compounds (**d**) and (**e**) but in this case proton-3 is only *ortho*-coupling and gives a very intense signal at high fields. The signal of the protons of CH_3 group is shifted to higher field on substituting the second CH_3 group by a phenyl one. The proton-6 exhibits its signal at lower field than that of proton-5 due to the electron-acceptor properties of the neighbouring $C=O$ group.

TABLE 2— 1H NMR SPECTRAL DATA OF BIS-AZO- β -DIKETONE DERIVATIVES (a-e)

Compd.	δ (ppm)							
	H ¹	H ²	H ³	H ⁴	H ⁵	H ⁶	H ⁷	H ⁸
			—					(-C-OH)
a	1.9	2.53	7.4	7.25	—		6.74	14.68
b	2.2	2.68	7.15	6.25	7.99	7.6	7.34	14.74
c	—	—	7.44	6.9	8.2	7.7	7.51	13.55
d	—	2.5	7.52	—	—	—	—	14.98
e	3.52	2.20	6.43	—	7.95	7.62	—	8.2

Spectra in buffer solutions : The spectra of the compounds in buffer solutions containing 30% (v/v) dioxane give one or two bands having changed behaviour with varied pH of the medium. The spectra of compounds (**b**, **c**, **e**) exhibit a band at 380–415 nm. This band can be ascribed to an intermolecular charge transfer from the phenyl group to the carbonyl group which favours the enolisation of the compound. The extinction of this increases with increasing pH till pH = 7.27, and above which the absorbance of the band decreases with shift to shorter wavelength. The blue-shift of the band is attributed to ionisation of the enolisation of the compound and the increase of pH of the medium increases the percentage of the ionic species till at high pH where a very broad and low extinction band would appear. This behaviour can be attributed to the antagonising effect of the negative charge on the enolic oxygen in the CT interaction. A new band appears at $\lambda_{max} = 325$ nm by increasing pH of the medium. The appearance of the band is due to the formation of the ionic species in equilibrium with the nonionic one. This behaviour for bis-azo compounds can be attributed to the existence of an acid-base equilibrium as shown in Scheme 2.

The pK_a values of the compounds (Table 3) are obtained by making use of the variation of absorbance with pH and applying the half-height⁸, modified limiting absorbance⁹ and Colleter methods¹⁰. The values of pK_a can be explained in relation to the molecular structure of the

bis-azo compound. The pK_a values of OH group of the enolic compound decrease on substituting CH_3 by phenyl ring. This can be interpreted on the basis that the electron-donating character of CH_3 group (sp^3) lowers the ionisation of the enolic OH group than in case of the donor-acceptor phenyl ring (sp^2). The free energy change ΔG° values for such ionisations have been determined from the pK_a values.

TABLE 3—IONISATION CONSTANT OF BISAZO- β -DIKETONE DERIVATIVES (a-e) IN 30% DIOXANE-BUFFER MEDIA

Compd.	pK_a			Average	ΔG° kcal mol^{-1}
	1st method	2nd method	3rd method		
a	10.9	10.92	11.08	10.97	14.932
b	8.42	8.48	8.52	8.47	11.550
c	7.6	7.57	7.54	7.57	10.32
d	11.24	11.35	11.73	11.43	15.600
e	9.68	9.68	9.61	9.66	13.17

Experimental

The bis-azo compounds, i.e. *m*- and *p*-bisazobenzene-di(β -diketone) were prepared by the usual method via diazotisation and coupling¹¹. Purity of the compounds was checked by m.p. and analytical data.

The solvents (commercial grade) were purified according to recommended procedures¹¹. The buffers used for pH control were members of the universal series of Britton and Robinson¹² containing 30% (v/v) dioxane. $10^{-3}M$ solutions of the dyes were prepared by dissolving the recrystallised product in the appropriate volume

of pure solvent. Solutions for spectral measurements were obtained by accurate dilution of the stock ones.

Electronic spectra at 25° were recorded on a Bausch-Lomb spectronic 21 spectrophotometer, ir spectra (KBr) on a Beckman 4220 spectrophotometer and ^1H nmr spectra on a Varian EM 390-90 spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard and CDCl_3 (for a-d) and DMSO-d_6 (for e) as a solvents. pH was measured on an Orion Research 601A pH meter.

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